

Scientists call for ambitious Sustainable Use of Pesticides Regulation

The heavy use of pesticides in agriculture is strongly linked to declines in insects, birds, biodiversity in terrestrial and aquatic systems and detrimental impacts on global public health. For that reason, the global reduction of pesticides use is one of the key negotiation points during the UN Biodiversity Summit (COP15) in Montréal. The European Commission has taken a leading role in efforts to curb pesticides by adopting a 50% reduction target of use and risks by 2030 in its [Farm to Fork Strategy](#). Earlier this year, the European Commission proposed [a Sustainable Use of Pesticides Regulation](#) to enshrine this target into legislation, as well as to mandate Member States to invest in Integrated Pest Management and ban pesticides from sensitive areas.

Given the urgent need for reduction of pesticide impacts, it is worrying to observe that a number of Member State governments and Members of the European Parliament have recently called for the delay and/or watering down of the new pesticides regulation. Citing [questionable](#) ‘food security’ and ‘resilience’ concerns, Member States have [called](#) for an additional impact assessment to the thorough assessment performed by the Commission before the outbreak of the Ukraine war. As members of the scientific community, we express our deep concern.

We stress that:

- The undelayed realisation of the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies’ pesticides reduction objectives remains of utmost importance to stop and reverse the decline of biodiversity.
- The “[Potsdam Statement](#)” of earlier this year remains unreservedly valid. This statement, signed by 600+ researchers, stressed the need to take demand-side actions in order to future-proof the EU’s food system, as such mitigating pressures on global biodiversity and sustaining the foundation for long-term food security.
- The gain in knowledge of the required additions to the thorough Impact Assessment performed by the European Commission is highly questionable, as the long-term challenges facing the EU food system and state of biodiversity have not changed since the outbreak of the war in Ukraine.
- Lack of binding targets is exactly the reason why investments in Integrated Pest Management have [lagged](#) behind since the adoption of the 2009 Pesticides Directive. The adoption of binding targets and a reallocation of public resources is [expected](#) to [accelerate innovation](#) of non-hazardous pesticide alternatives.
- A food system transition is non-linear and disruptive by definition. While current modes of impact assessment may provide insights into short-term market impacts, they are [incapable](#) of projecting longer-term innovation and disruption, which the Green Deal aims for.

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234. Dr. Maarten Schrama, Assistant Professor, Department of Environmental Biology, Institute of Environmental Sciences, Leiden University, The Netherlands.
235. Dr. Adrian Muller, Dept. of Food System Sciences, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Switzerland
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239. Dr Ulrich Loening, retired Reader in Molecular Biology and Director of the Centre for Human Ecology, University of Edinburgh
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241. Assoc.-Prof. PD Dipl.-Ing. Dr. med. Hans-Peter Hutter, Department of Environmental Health, Center for Public Health, Medical University Vienna, Austria.
242. Prof. Dr.. Gloria I. Guzmán. Professor of Agroecology and Organic Farming. Agroecosystems History Laboratory. Pablo de Olavide University (Spain).
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244. Prof. Dr. Josef Settele, Co-Chair of IPBES Global Assessment; Member of the German Advisory Council on the Environment - SRU; German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig; Dept. of Conservation Biology and Social-Ecological Systems, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Halle, Germany.
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247. Prof. dr. ir. Cees J.N. Buisman, Executive Board Wetsus and professor Biological Recovery Wageningen..
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282. Dr. Tomaso Ferrando, Research Professor, University of Antwerp Faculty of Law, Belgium
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339. Prof. Dr. Violette Geissen, Wageningen University, Netherlands
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378. Dr. Sarah Jones, Scientist, Multifunctional Landscapes team, Alliance of Bioversity International and CIAT
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470. Angela Schwarm, Associate Professor, Department of Animal and Aquacultural Sciences, Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Norway.
471. Malcom Ferdinand, CNRS University Paris Dauphine-PSL
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480. Dr. Clelia Sirami, Researcher INRAE, France
481. Dr Sylvaine Lemeilleur, Researcher, CIRAD, UMR MOISA, Montpellier, France
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485. Dr. Bernard Dumas, CNRS researcher Plant Biology, head LRSV UMR, Toulouse, France
486. Dr. Alberto Sanz Cobeña, Professor. UPM, Spain
487. Prof. Olivier De Schutter, Catholic University of Louvain (Belgium) and Sciences Po (France)
488. Dr. Britta Uhl, Goethe University Frankfurt, Institute of Ecology, Diversity and Evolution, Germany
489. Dr. Mirko Wölfling, independent researcher (Bio-advice), former University of Vienna, Austria
490. Dr Christian Schöb, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain
491. Prof Dr Luc De Meester, IGB (Berlin, Germany), Freie Universität Berlin (Germany), KU Leuven (Belgium)
492. Dr. Cristina Armas, Estación Experimental de Zonas Áridas, CSIC. Spanish National Research Council. Spain.
493. Dr. Eve Bureau-Point, Researcher, CNRS, Centre Norbert Elias, Marseille, France
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622. Benjamin Andreu , PhD Student, Université Paris-Saclay, Gif-sur-Yvette, France
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631. Dr Anna Zaidman-Rémy, Associate Professor INSA-Lyon, France
632. Dr Claire Villemant, Attachée honoraire, Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France
633. Dr Emilie Le Goff, Université de Montpellier, France
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635. Prof. Julien Royet. Aix Marseille Université, France
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647. DI Stefan Lefnaer; Austrian Association for Floristic Research; co-author of the Austrian Red List of ferns and flowering plants 2022, Vienna, Austria
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652. Dr. Simon Fellous, research Director, Pest control, INRAEP, France
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654. Dr Errol Vela, Associate Professor, biodiversity and botany, university of Montpellier, France

655. Gabriela Rabeschini, PhD student, Senckenberg Biodiversity and Climate Research Center, Frankfurt am Main, Germany
656. Dr. Demetrios Kouretas, Professor Biochemical Toxicology, University of Thessaly, Greece, President of Greek Toxicology Society
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659. Dr. Jérémy Gauthier, Museum of Geneva, Switzerland.
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714. Dr Christine Malfay-Regnier, President of the association SOS MCS, Valence France.
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